

"Use of vibrations to manipulate the behaviour of the meadow spittlebug *Philaenus spumarius*"

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Sexually mature adults of the meadow spittlebug, *Philaenus spumarius* (Linn.), exchange vibrational signals through the host plants to communicate and achieve mating. Novel pest control strategies involve the manipulation of the sexual behaviour of the insect by means of species-specific mechanical stimuli transmitted to plants. Playback trials with mini-shakers were conducted to evaluate if the transmission of pre-recorded *P. spumarius* vibrational signals to a plant of *Helianthus annuus* could affect the behaviour of the insect and to evaluate the potential use of vibrations for management practices against this pest. In all the trials, vibrational signals emitted by the specimens were recorded with laser vibrometer. *P. spumarius* males and females were tested with playback of two types of male calling signal, which are spontaneously emitted by males since their emergence in spring and differ for the presence/absence of pulses within them. The playbacks were played in June-July (n=30) and in September-October (n=20) to evaluate whether the role of the signals could depend on the time of the season. In August and September, pairs consisting of a female and a male were released on different leaves of a *H. annuus* plant and stimulated either with the playback of pre-recorded signals such as the male rivalry signal (n=20) or the FRjS (n=20) or with a broadband noise (n=20) to disrupt the pair formation process. Results of all the playback trials are presented as well as a fine description of the mating behaviour of the meadow spittlebug. Insights on the potential future development of more sustainable control strategies against this pest are given.